

THE MOMENTUM OF CHINA-UZBEKISTAN JOINT DEVELOPMENT UNDER "BELT AND ROAD" INITIATIVE

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The "Belt and Road" initiative has been in progress for over a decade. With the joint efforts of all parties, the initiative has evolved from a Chinese proposal to an international practice, from an idea into action, and from a vision into reality. It has become a widely welcomed international platform for cooperation, making positive contributions to the healthy development of economic globalization, addressing global development challenges, and improving the global governance system.

I. The Belt and Road Initiative has placed the development of China-Uzbekistan relations at a new historical starting point.

Uzbekistan has had relations with China for over 2,000 years. Numerous nomadic tribes have risen and fallen on this fertile land. With the proposal of the "Belt and Road" initiative, the ancient Silk Road is set to be infused with new vitality. Uzbekistan, an inland country located in the central and northern part of Central Asia, has had interactions with China for more than two millennia. After gaining independence, Uzbekistan and China established diplomatic relations on January 2, 1992. Uzbekistan was the first Central Asian country to establish diplomatic ties with China. Today, China is one of the main trade and investment partners of Uzbekistan, and the two countries have also engaged in extensive cooperation in the fields of culture, education, and science and technology. The Silk Road, connecting the East and the West, has been an important medium for dialogue between different civilizations since ancient times. With the introduction of the "Belt and Road" initiative by China in 2013, the joint development of the two countries has stood at a new historical starting point.

Uzbekistan is an important participant in the China-Central Asia cooperation mechanism. It is also continuously deepening its involvement in the construction of electric power infrastructure. Xinjiang TBEA Group Corporation began operations in Uzbekistan in 2005. In 2023, the Shaudari and 135+50 MW hydropower station projects in Uzbekistan were fully completed and officially put into use, greatly alleviating the electricity shortage for agricultural irrigation in Samarkand and providing electricity security. This has reduced electricity costs and provided a reliable power supply for local development, as well as a large number of job opportunities. In September 2022, China's Goldwind Technology successfully signed

a contract for a 521MW wind power project in Uzbekistan. Once completed, the project will significantly improve the local power structure and reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 1.1 million tons annually, helping Uzbekistan achieve its goal of increasing the share of green electricity to 25% by 2030.

In Tashkent, Uzbekistan, on the streets, one cannot help but notice the stylish and high-performance "Made in China" new energy vehicles. In 2023, Uzbekistan purchased about 20,000 electric vehicles from China, accounting for approximately 93% of its total electric vehicle imports and 34% of the total number of vehicles imported from China. On October 9, 2024, NIO officially launched the NIO X in Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan, and its first flagship store in the Central Asian market will also commence operations, marking NIO's official entry into the Central Asian market. In fact, China almost covers the entire import electric vehicle market of Uzbekistan. This is not only because China is the world's largest electric vehicle market, but also mainly due to the continuous deepening of economic and trade cooperation between China and Uzbekistan, which creates a favorable environment for Chinese electric vehicles to enter the Uzbek market.

Cultural and people-to-people cooperation plays a unique and significant role in the development of China-Kyrgyzstan relations. In recent years, exchanges between China and Kyrgyzstan in the fields of culture, education, health, women's affairs, youth, and sports have become increasingly frequent, and the mechanisms and platforms for cooperation have been continuously enriched, further deepening the exchanges and understanding between the peoples of the two countries. Riding the momentum of the "Belt and Road" initiative, both sides are building a closer China-Kyrgyzstan community with a shared future, continuing to promote the high-quality development of "Belt and Road".

II. Key Drivers of China-Uzbekistan Relations under the "Belt and Road" Initiative

Firstly, a high level of political mutual trust provides a solid political foundation for the steady and long-term development of China-Uzbekistan relations. Central Asian countries are all landlocked, with Uzbekistan being one of the only two double landlocked countries in the world (a landlocked country whose neighbors are also landlocked). For a long time, factors such as insufficient coverage of regional railway networks, relatively lagging domestic infrastructure construction, and inconvenient external transportation have hindered the economic development of Central Asian countries. Both sides, adhering to the original intention of establishing diplomatic relations, actively work to implement the important consensus reached between the two countries, and firmly support each other on issues involving each other's core interests. As early as the 1990s, China and Uzbekistan proposed the idea

of a China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway. In 1997, the construction plan for the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway was first proposed by the "Transport Corridor Europe-Caucasus-Asia (TRACECA)" organization. In the same year, China, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan signed a memorandum of cooperation on the construction of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway. Today, the project has made significant progress—In June 2024, the signing ceremony for the intergovernmental agreement on the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway project was held in Beijing. This event has become a symbol of strengthening regional transportation connectivity and also signifies that the construction of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway will finally begin in a substantive manner.

Secondly, the high-quality joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative has built a broad platform for cooperation between China and Uzbekistan in various fields. In recent years, pragmatic cooperation between China and Uzbekistan has been continuously expanding and has yielded fruitful results. Trade and economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and China has been steadily growing. In July 2024, a provisional summary of bilateral trade for the first half of the year showed that the trade volume reached 5.9 billion US dollars. This figure indicates a high growth rate, surpassing that of previous years. China remains Uzbekistan's largest trading partner, confirming the strategic importance of the Chinese market to Uzbekistan's economy. China actively invests in Uzbekistan's infrastructure construction, which is also reflected in the implementation of modernization projects for transportation hubs. In September 2024, new agreements were signed, confirming Chinese investors' willingness to participate in the creation of logistics centers and the modernization of railway infrastructure. This will enhance the competitiveness of Uzbekistani goods in the international market and accelerate economic integration with China and other countries. Another key area of bilateral cooperation is energy projects. Chinese companies are actively involved in the development of renewable energy in Uzbekistan. In August 2024, new agreements were signed for the construction of solar and wind power plants. These projects not only strengthen Uzbekistan's energy security but also create new opportunities for job creation and environmental improvement in the region.

The joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative between China and Uzbekistan continues to deepen and solidify, providing a stable platform for cooperation in various fields and promoting increasingly frequent friendly exchanges at all levels between the two sides.

Thirdly, building a China-Uzbekistan community with a shared future opens up a bright future for the development of China-Uzbekistan relations. Both sides recognize the concept of a community with a shared future for mankind

and the "Belt and Road" initiative. They firmly support each other on issues related to national sovereignty, security, and territorial integrity, which are core interests for both, and oppose the politicization of human rights issues by third countries. The Chinese side firmly supports the peaceful, open, and pragmatic foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its efforts to promote stability and common prosperity in the Central Asian region. China always supports Uzbekistan's independent choice of development path and is willing to provide help within its capabilities to support Uzbekistan's smooth progress in modernization and the reform of economic and social policies, which are major domestic agendas. The Uzbekistan firmly supports the One-China principle, reaffirms that the Government of the People's Republic of China is the only legitimate government representing all of China and Firmly support the peaceful development of cross-strait relations and firmly support all efforts made by the Chinese government to achieve national unification.

Additionally, the two sides closely collaborate within the frameworks of the United Nations, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and the China-Central Asia mechanism. This not only summarizes the outcomes of the many years of development of bilateral relations but also outlines the future prospects for these relations. It is based on the profound political trust, fruitful cooperation achievements, and strong emotional bonds between the two countries, and also demonstrates the confidence and determination of both sides for their future joint development and prosperity.

III. Embarking on the Path of Cooperation, Friendship, and Development

Firstly, as a path of cooperation, the joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative has significantly propelled the development of China-Uzbekistan relations. In recent years, the two sides have signed dozens of bilateral cooperation documents covering various fields such as economy and trade, investment, connectivity, customs, agriculture, people-to-people exchanges, and security. The "Belt and Road" initiative has provided strong momentum for practical cooperation between China and Uzbekistan. For instance, in the field of cultural archaeology, through the collaboration of experts from both sides, the restoration project of historical and cultural relics in Khorezm has been completed, and significant breakthroughs have been made in joint archaeological projects such as the Mingtepe ancient city site in the Fergana Valley. The regular operation of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan highway has become a major transportation artery in the Central Asian region.

The high-quality joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative not only serves as an important practical platform for promoting the development of a community with a shared future between China and Uzbekistan, but also forms a vital

platform for pragmatic cooperation between the two countries. It has continuously improved the quality and efficiency of cooperation in economic trade, cultural exchanges, and other fields. Moreover, it has effectively debunked the so-called "debt trap theory" and "China threat theory" in Kyrgyzstan, making these anti-China fallacies collapse under their own weight.

Secondly, as a path of friendship, the joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative continuously deepens the connection between the peoples of the two countries. People-to-people bonds are an essential aspect of the "Belt and Road" construction and form the social foundation for its advancement. The Uzbek edition of "How to Escape Poverty" was published and distributed in Uzbekistan at the end of last year, serving as a vivid example of the in-depth exchange of governance experience between the two countries.

The "Chinese culture craze" and "Chinese language fever" continue to gain momentum in Uzbekistan. Confucius Institutes have taken root in Tashkent and Samarkand, cultivating a large number of Chinese language talents in Uzbekistan. Over 20 educational institutions in Uzbekistan offer Chinese language majors, while numerous universities in China have introduced Uzbek language majors. Chinese TV dramas such as "Romance of the Three Kingdoms" have sparked a viewing frenzy in Uzbekistan, and Uzbekistan's classic literary works have been introduced to Chinese readers. Exchanges and mutual visits by various artistic groups from both countries have brought splendid performances to the people of both sides.

All of these have fostered mutual understanding among the people. In fact, China and Uzbekistan are friendly neighbors sharing a common destiny. No matter how the international situation changes, the relationship between the two countries has always developed healthily and steadily, maintaining strong vitality and dynamism.

Thirdly, as a path of development, the joint construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative effectively promotes the development and revitalization of both parties. China and Uzbekistan actively promote the alignment of the "Belt and Road" initiative with Uzbekistan's national development strategy, fully leveraging geographical advantages to create a comprehensive and diverse pattern of joint development.

China has long maintained its position as Uzbekistan's largest trading partner and a major source of investment. According to Chinese customs statistics, the bilateral trade volume exceeded 14 billion US dollars in 2023, with a year-on-year increase of over 40%. China's cumulative investment in Uzbekistan has surpassed 14 billion US dollars, with more than 2,300 Chinese enterprises operating in the country. From the Central Asia's longest tunnel, the "Angren-Pap" railway tunnel, to

Uzbekistan's highest standard A380 highway currently under construction, from the Pengsheng Industrial Park to the Olympic City project, and from photovoltaic and wind power clean energy projects to Chinese new energy vehicles traveling on local streets, these initiatives deeply reflect the continuous deepening of practical cooperation between the two countries.

In conclusion, "A single flower does not make a spring, but a hundred flowers in full bloom bring spring to the garden." Civilizations thrive on diversity, exchange, and mutual learning. Under the "Belt and Road" initiative, the future development of China and Uzbekistan is full of momentum and promise.

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